

ISSN: 2582-7561

**International Journal For Academic
Research & Development**

Vol. 4 (2022)

ISSUE 2

(Multidisciplinary)

E-mail Id: editor@iifard.org

url: www.iifard.org/about-journal/

www.iifard.org

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR ACADEMIC RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

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ISSN: 2582-7561

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**Volume 4, Issue 2
2022**

Published by

International Institute For Academic Research and Development

Email: trustforacademic@gmail.com, editor@iifard.org

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ISSN: 2582-7561

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Fire fighting Robot

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Abstract: Fire plays an important role in human life, but it also poses a risk. A fire disaster can result in loss of life, property damage, and long-term disability for those affected. Firefighters are primarily responsible for dealing with fires, but they often face additional risks when quenching them. Particularly in dangerous environments, such as nuclear power plants, oil treatment facilities, and gas tanks. When dealing with a fire in a small area, it's crucial to investigate structures and obstructions to extinguish the fire and protect the person. This paper presents advancements in firefighting. Robots using embedded systems that can extinguish fire without Firefighters must fulfill certain requirements. This Puts out flames the robot is equipped with fire detection sensors, smoke sensors, and temperature sensors to monitor surrounding areas. Movement is controlled via Bluetooth and the robot is customized to detect fires. We are attempting to provide a specialized answer to the previously mentioned issue.

Keywords: Robot, Fire fighting

1. Introduction

A robot is a machine that resembles a person and performs various complex tasks. There are numerous types of robots. Here, a FIRE Quenching ROBOT is proposed. The robot has a fire sensor that detects ecological fires and sends signals to the microcontroller. The siphon then sprinkles water to extinguish the fire. This robot works with an Arduino Uno microcontroller. This robot embodies the concepts of natural fire detection and engine control. The engine driver enables bidirectional control of the robot's engines. The robot receives guidance for movement control via a microcontroller.

The robot collects data from various equipment components, including fire sensors and an ARDUINO Uno board (microcontroller). The robot is programmed using Arduino, a C and C++ based programming language. This project is introduced as an additional proposed methodology in the given segment, which includes a block diagram, components, and their clarification.

Details about equipment and programming are included, as well as results and goals. The goal of our project is to identify fire in disaster-prone territory. Additionally, provides sound and visual signals. Stifles fire upon identification. Reduces human labor and decimation. The robot will detect fire in its surroundings and follow the microcontroller's instructions.

2. SYSTEM DESIGN IMPLEMENTATION: -

The primary goal of this project is to locate the natural fire and use a water siphon to put it out. The ATmega328P is required for the Arduino UNO R3 Microcontroller board to function. An appropriate platform for applying autonomy is the ATmega328P. This allows for the continuous smothering of the fire.

As opposed to other controller programming, Arduino is much simpler and is derived from C and C++ programming.

The extinguishing system is in turn controlled by the microcontroller. The controller's working voltage is 5 volts, its clock speed is 16 MHz, and its recommended information voltage is 7 to 12 volts, with 6 to 20 volts range. The main goal of this project is to construct a programmed robot that uses an Arduino to identify fire and sprinklers to put it out when the siphon is triggered. The engine driver board represents the direction of the robot's development.

It is used to supply high voltage and high current as a yield to power the engines used in the robotics development project. Currently, a simple DC engine is used to pivot the wheel, which is responsible for the robot's development. Generally speaking, DC engines transform electrical energy into mechanical energy. An easy-to-use motor is used to pump water onto the fire using a siphon to put out the flames. The extinguishing system's pumping motor regulates the water flow that emerges from the pump.

3. HARDWARE/COMPONENT: -

3.1 ARDUINO: The Arduino Uno is the project's central nervous system. We use flame sensors, also called fire sensors, to detect fire. These sensors use infrared (IR) light, which is released when a fire burns, to detect the presence of fire. This is how it operates: Flame Sensors: Three flame sensors are positioned on the robot in various directions. Every sensor has a photodiode (IR receiver) that picks up infrared light that the fire emits. The output pin (DO) of the sensor goes low (0V) to indicate the presence of fire when a fire is detected. *Motor Control:* The robot is equipped with four wheels, which it controls with an L293D motor driver module. The robot advances toward the fire by directing its motors in the proper direction when its sensors pick up the fire.

Water Pump and Nozzle: The robot is equipped with a tiny DC submersible pump and a small water container. To regulate the direction of the water spray, the water container is set atop a servo motor. The water pump is turned on by the robot when it gets close to the fire, putting out the flames.

3.2 GEAR MOTOR: DC motor with wheel: For this project, a DC-gear motor with a rubber wheel would be appropriate. Two-wheel and four-wheel drive car chassis can be replaced with this DC motor. A DC motor can operate between 5 and 10 volts DC. whereas the gear ratio is 48:1. 73.2 mA is the appropriate current for this motor. The robot is moved to the fire location by a DC motor.

Speed-100RPM
Voltage-12Volt
Horsepower-5watt's
Materials-Alloy steel

3.3 FLAME SENSOR: This sensor uses light wavelengths between 760 and 1100 nanometers to detect flames. The flame size and sensitivity settings determine the test distance. There are 60 degrees in the detection angle.

Barrier and obstacle avoidance is one of the most important aspects of creating an autonomous target detection robot. A sensor needs to be small, inexpensive, easy to manufacture, and large-scale functional. It should also have sufficient sensing limits to enable robots to respond and move accordingly. Ultrasonic sensors are currently available and meet all of these criteria. The distance in this study is measured using the HCSR04 ultrasonic sensor at a 15-degree angle and a range of 2 to 400 cm. This sensor sends waves into space and picks up waves that are reflected from the object. It has four output pins: ground, digital, analog, and reference voltage (which operates at roughly 5V).

The kind of sensor that reacts to ambient light the strongest is a flame sensor. As a result, flame alarms use this sensor module. **This sensor detects flames from the light source with wavelengths between 760 and 1100 nm.** This sensor is susceptible to damage from high temperatures. Thus, the location of this sensor can be chosen to be a certain distance from the flame. At 100 centimeters, one can detect the flame. Either a digital or an analog signal can be output by this sensor. These sensors are used by firefighting robots as a flame alert.

3.4 12V & 9V BATTERY: The choice of battery is essential for firefighting robots because it must deliver dependable power to the water pump, sensors, and motors. Because of their high energy density and efficiency, rechargeable batteries like Li-ion or LFP cells are typically used by these robots.

For instance, the robot and a 12 V DC pump might be powered by a single 12 V battery to perform axial and suction water spraying¹. The robot's size and the anticipated length of its operation will determine the battery's capacity.

A Battery Management System (BMS) for safety and effective charging, as well as battery support brackets to safely hold the batteries in place while the robot is operating, may also be included in the battery system ².

To create a robot that can autonomously detect and put out fires, you would need to take into account these parts in addition to an Arduino Uno, flame sensors, a robot chassis, motors, a water tank, and a nozzle³.

3.5 12V TO 5V REGULATOR: A voltage regulator integrated circuit (IC) such as the 7805 can be used to integrate a 12V to 5V regulator into a firefighting robot. This integrated circuit (IC) can convert 12V input into a stable 5V output, which is frequently needed to power low-voltage components like sensors and Arduino boards that are part of the control circuitry.

3.6 MOTOR DRIVER IC L298: Popular motor driver integrated circuits (ICs) like the L298 are used in many robotic applications, such as firefighting robots. With this dual H-Bridge motor driver, you can independently adjust the speed and direction of two DC motors. It is capable of handling peak currents of up to 2A1 and is appropriate for driving motors at voltages between 5V and 35V.

The L298 can be used to regulate both the water pump's function and the robot's movement in a firefighting robot. The robot can navigate toward the fire and turn on the pump to put it out thanks to the IC. The robot's actions are controlled by an Arduino board, which is connected to the motor driver. The Arduino board receives input from sensors, such as a flame sensor that detects fire.

4. WORKING: -

A computer vision algorithm powers the main fire detection system. In this system, we used the Python OpenCV module to find fire in the feed from the camera. Each frame of the camera feed is scanned, and the program determines whether there is a fire by analysing the color code of the screen pixels that fall within a given range of the HSV (Hue Saturation Value) color scale values. The program successfully detects the presence of fire if the color code is within this predetermined range.

Sensors are the basis for the secondary fire detection system's operation. Upon receiving a signal from the primary fire detection system, the secondary system initiates operations. It is made up of gas, smoke, or flame sensors that measure things and use a pre-set algorithm to determine whether or not there is a fire. A buzzer sounds and a water jet is started via a relay circuit if every sensor indicates that there is a fire.

A Bluetooth module in this system allows for remote control of the robot. The robot can be instructed to move forward, backward, left, right, and stop. As they move through the surroundings, the Collision avoidance mechanisms are incorporated into the algorithm, allowing the robot to avoid obstacles and stop moving if it detects one.

Mostly using visual sensors, firefighting robots locate and detect flames and then proceed with rescue and firefighting operations based on this information.

The Fire Fighting Robot continuously measures the temperature at three different sensors. If there is a fire, the robot moves in the direction where the temperature is recorded as being the highest among the four sensors and uses a water pump to put out the fire consists of a geared motor, water pump, temperature sensor, smoke sensor, and flame sensor. These sensors allow the robot to continuously monitor changes in its surroundings.

4. RESULT: -

- 4.1 The precision with which our computer vision algorithm detects flames and surrounds them with bounding boxes demonstrates its efficacy in this area. The secondary system thoroughly confirms the existence of the fire after the primary system has detected it.
- 4.2 If the backup system verifies the existence of fire, the robot can move through the flaming area by following the manual directions provided by the Android device.
- 4.3 The pump is a crucial component in putting out a fire, and the robot starts to activate it when it detects one.
- 4.4 The robot is capable of being remotely controlled from a significant distance, with an effective range of up to 6 meters.

5. COST ESTIMATION: -

Sr.no	Name of components used	Quantity	Cost component (Rs.)
1	Gear Motor	4	640
2	9v & 12v Battery	2	220
3	Arduino UNO	1	690
4	Flame Sensor (IR SENSOR)	3	990
5	Water pump	1	159
6	Connecting Wire	5m	100
7	Wheel	4	800
8	Body sheet	1	250
9	Water Tank	1	150
10	Switch	1	20
11	12V To 5V Regulator	1	399
12	Motor Driver IC L298	2	900
			Total Cost = 5318

6. ADVANTAGES: -

- 6.1 Firefighters may not need to enter as many hazardous situations when there are robots around.
- 6.2 Even the most seasoned firefighters encounter circumstances that are too risky or challenging for them to handle alone.
- 6.3 The robot is a reputable robot manufacturer with an emphasis on creating and designing firefighting robots.
- 6.4 Cut Down on the Danger to Human Life.
- 6.5 Quicker Reaction Time.

7. CONCLUSION: -

- 7.1 With this project, we hope to lessen the impact of fire incidents, which typically originate from tiny flames, saving both lives and money.
- 7.2 The robot can locate the fire and get there without encountering any difficulties.
- 7.3 We created the FIRE EXTINGUISHER Robot with success. The robot's location allows it to sense temperature, flame, and smoke.
- 7.4 The MCU controls this robot vehicle's movement by the program.

- 7.5 This robot comes in handy in places where bomb explosions and natural disasters happen.
- 7.6 In conclusion, the Arduino-based firefighting robot has shown to be a dependable and successful firefighting tool. The simulated and real-world scenarios have showcased the robot's capability to identify fires, maneuver around obstacles, and put out fires.
- 7.7 Future advancements in thermal imaging, swarm robotics, and machine learning algorithms may make firefighting robots even more useful weapons in the battle against fires.

8. FUTURE SCOPE: -

- 8.1 Remote control of the robot. And Video transmission can be added. Improve the weight capacity of the robot.
- 8.2 Select the suitable material to develop the robot.
- 8.3 The development of programming is necessary to develop a mechanism for the robot.
- 8.4 Swarm robotics can be used to build a group of firefighting robots that can cooperate to put out big fires. Every robot will have an internet connection to a central computer or server, from which actuation commands will be generated based on algorithms.
- 8.5 Integration of solar panels: The robot can continue examining the fire scene without needing to recharge its batteries thanks to the integration of solar panels.
- 8.6 Integration of nozzle angle control: To regulate the water jet's targeting on a fire, water nozzle controllers can be added. This will increase efficiency by lowering the amount of water and other fire-extinguishing material wasted.

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